

Original Article

Intersectionality and Student Inclusion in Higher Education: A Study of Class, Residence, Culture, and Extracurricular Participation

Muhammad Shoaib¹, Iqra Tariq², & Shamraiz Iqbal³¹ Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, University of Gujrat, Gujrat, Punjab, Pakistan.² BS Student, Department of Sociology, University of Gujrat, Gujrat, Punjab, Pakistan.³ PhD Scholar, Department of Gender Studies, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Abstract

This paper analyzes intersectionality and student inclusion in higher education by the predictors including class, residence, culture, and extracurricular participation. It is obvious that different intersecting dimensions shape a sense of belonging, students' access to opportunities, and participation within academic spaces, the research seeks to provide a nuanced understanding of diversity and inclusion practices in higher education institutions. The students of sociology and economics comprise the population of the study and a total unit of analysis has been reported as 644 on the day of sampling frame collection. A sample of 213 students has been selected through proportionate random sampling techniques. A cross-section study has been conducted using a structured questionnaire having different sections. An attitudinal scale of (dis)agreement has been used to measure the responses of the students. Pilot testing has been done to check the reliability of the tool i.e. Alpha values .700 and above. The data analysis has been presented based on the Chi-Square and regression analysis statistical tests. The study findings assert that the intersectionality of class, residential background, cultural differences, and extracurricular activities have favorable effects on the diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The study findings also revealed that extracurricular activities have familiar effects on creating diversity and inclusion among students in higher education.

Keywords: Extracurricular Activities, Diversity, Inclusivity, Students Competitions, Higher Education

Introduction

It has been observed that an inclusive environment is very important for students in higher education. In this regard, extracurricular activities play an essential role in providing equal access to resources for students from different genders, backgrounds, religions, and residential areas (Arshad, Anwar, & Shoaib, 2024a; Vandell et al., 2022). These activities help students interact with peers outside the classroom. Students learn the benefits of teamwork and are involved in discussions and debates on different topics (Boone, Natasha, & Smith, 2023; Shoaib, Ali, Anwar, et al., 2021). Through participating in these activities, students also change their perspectives and develop mutual understanding, and respect for diverse identities (Ali, Zaman, & Shoaib, 2024; Berger, Cristian, & Espelage, 2021). However, all students have less equal access to participating in extracurricular activities due to structural and cultural barriers (Shoaib, 2021).

Extracurricular activities included sports festivals, students' get-togethers, quiz competitions, volunteer activities, and outdoor non-academic activities. It has been observed that sports festivals have been celebrated by students at all educational levels in developed and developing countries (Park, Jia, & Kim, 2023). These events are organized by the university for the students. These festivals have a variety of activities, including indoor and outdoor (Shoaib, 2024e). The sports activities have been linked with the active participation of students. Students enjoy these activities and release the burden of their studies. Sports festivals are an integral tradition in universities that offer students fun activities and remarkable memories (Katsogridakis & Leather, 2025; Luguetti, Anne, & André, 2019; Wang & Chen, 2021). It has been mentioned that quiz and debate competitions are an essential part

JOURNAL OF
SOCIAL HORIZONS

Copyright © The Author(s). 2025

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited.

How to Cite:

Shoaib, M., Tariq, I., & Iqbal, S. (2025). Intersectionality and Student Inclusion in Higher Education: A Study of Class, Residence, Culture, and Extracurricular Participation. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 2(1), 1-10.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15650554>

* Corresponding Author: Muhammad Shoaib | Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, University of Gujrat, Gujrat, Punjab, Pakistan.

✉ shoaibsoc@uog.edu.pk

© 2025 | College of Education, Swabi, Pakistan.

of extracurricular activities at the educational level. These competitions are organized by the academic societies and cover a range of topics. Students participated in these competitions and prepared their debates with strong points. Quiz competitions check the knowledge of the students and state updates about current affairs (Abernathy & Forestal, 2020; Shoaib, 2024c). Some students enjoy these competitions as the audience. This competition is a respected event in university calendars and promotes the academic environment in universities (Bourner & Heath, 2014; Cook & Babon, 2017; Stamelos, 2011).

Diversity and inclusion have become a fundamental aspect of higher education. Age and gender the important factors in university life. The university welcomes all age and gender groups. Age is linked with the year of study, maturity level, and perspectives of students. All age groups received equal access to resources and opportunities in university (Shoaib & Zaman, 2025; Singer & Cunningham, 2012). Male and female students received equal levels of respect and equal representation in higher education. University design policies to minimize discrimination and break down the traditional stereotypes related to gender and age (Montepare, Anne, & Dixon, 2019; Silverstein, Meghan, Marshall, & Whitbourne, 2019; Villa-Lever, 2020). It has been observed that universities promoted neutrality for political parties. Students feel free to share their political views in a university environment. Students freely align themselves with a specific political party. The university provided space for students to express their political views and share with others. Students voice their opinions and actively participate in political rallies. University provided a deeper understanding of political affairs and democratic processes among students (Ahmad, 2020; Hlavac, 2016; Schönwälder, 2020). Hence, this study has been designed to examine intersectionality and student inclusion in higher education by the predictors including class, residence, culture, and extracurricular participation.

Review of Literature

Several studies have been conducted to examine the diversity and inclusivity of students in higher education (Shoaib, Shehzadi, & Abbas, 2024b). The analysis of the study pointed out that extracurricular activities had impacted diversity and social skill development among students (Zhang & Veacock, 2023). Similarly, the study findings outlined the influence of extracurricular activity on the differences based on the age and gender of the students in higher education (Shoaib, Shehzadi, & Abbas, 2024a; Zhang & Tang, 2017). Likewise, the research revealed that the role of age, race, and ethnicity affected the involvement of the students in extracurricular activities (Shoaib, Ali, & Abbas, 2024; Simpkins, & Price, 2012). Further, the analysis of the study showed that extracurricular activities, cultural orientation, and family resources among Latino students positively supported their study (Shoaib, 2024d; Simpkins, Megan, & Becnel, 2011). Moreover, the study asserted that the education system created diversity through extracurricular activities among students at the higher education level (Shoaib, 2024b; Yemini & Addi-Racciah, 2013). In the same way, the search findings argued that extracurricular activities break down the cultural barriers among university students (Shoaib, Zaman, & Abbas, 2024; Wong, 2023). As mentioned in the study analysis that extracurricular activities promoted inclusive social learning and social integration among university students (Shoaib, 2024a; Tlalajoe-Mokhatla, 2024). However, the study findings articulated that extracurricular activities promoted positive learning behaviors among diverse backgrounds of students in higher education (Ribeiro, Carla, Tiago, & Menezes, 2024).

The study findings clinched that extracurricular activities such as athletics, clubs, or music affected access to opportunities among higher education students (Kim & Bastedo, 2017; Shoaib, 2024a). Similarly, the study findings outlined that participating in curricular activities created a sense of belongingness, and respect for diversity at a high education level (Hordósy & Clark, 2018; Shoaib & Ullah, 2021). Likewise, the research revealed that the use of AI apps and extracurricular learning enhanced inclusivity in the compulsory education system (Cao, 2024; Shoaib & Ullah, 2019). Further, the crux of the study indicated that involvement in extracurricular activities promoted social connections and relationships among different students (Boone et al., 2023; Shoaib, Ali, & Akbar, 2021). Moreover, the study asserted that a strong relationship exists between extracurricular activities and plans among university students (Betz, Gay, & Redcay, 2005). In the same way, the search findings argued that a positive relationship existed between students' achievements, higher grades, and extracurricular activities (King, & Brigham, 2021; Shoaib, Usmani, & Abdullah, 2023). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that involvement in extracurricular activities was affected by the role of gender and social norms at the tertiary level (Berger et al., 2021; Shoaib, Iqbal, & Tahira, 2021). However, the study findings articulated that extracurricular activities support positive youth development and the role of meaningful engagement in society for students (Bundick, 2011).

The study pointed out that higher education institutes motivated students for extracurricular activities and outdoor non-academic activities (Chapman, Washad, & Obembe, 2023). Similarly, the study findings outlined that extracurricular activities played a role in building social skills and self-assessment among university students (Guest, Peter, & Maige, 2021). Likewise, the research revealed that taking part in extracurricular activities enhanced cross-cultural friendships and social connectedness in higher education (Darling, & Smith, 2005). Further, the analysis of the study indicated the role of multiple clubs in career and professional choices among students at the university level (Aliu & Aigbavboa, 2023). Moreover, the study asserted that taking part in extracurricular activities promoted active citizenship and affiliation with political parties (Keser, Hanife, & Yildirim, 2011). In the same way, the search findings argued that extracurricular activities positively affected socioemotional behavior and mental well-being (Metsäpelto & Pulkkinen, 2012). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that extracurricular activities given the chance of different backgrounds to represent themselves at university level (Xu & Hu, 2024). However, the study findings articulated that joining extracurricular activities enhanced the sense of belongingness among different residential backgrounds of the students in higher education (O'Donnell, Gerry, & Mooney, 2024).

The results of the study revealed that sports festivals promoted social inclusion and are the key to minimizing diversity at high education levels (Kwiatkowski, Ove, Anne-Mette, & Maristuen, 2020). Similarly, the study findings outlined that sports festivals enhanced physical activity and healthy lifestyles among students of different ages in high education (Hastie, & Wallhead, 2023). Likewise, the research revealed the role of national governing bodies in conducting sports festivals for all ages and genders at the tertiary level (Arshad, Anwar, & Shoaib, 2024b; Harris & Houlihan, 2016). Further, the crux of the study indicated that equal opportunities and inclusive participation of each gender in sports festivals in high education (Mackintosh, 2014; Shoaib, 2023). Moreover, the study asserted that sports festivals are influenced by different age, gender, and race groups at high education levels (Pill, Dawn, John, Vaughan, & Hyndman, 2023). In the same way, the search findings argued that sports festivals increased the well-being benefit and teamwork among students in higher education (Naseer, Shoaib, & Naseer, 2022; Storr & Spaaij, 2017). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that physical education and sports festivals as a bridge between cultural and social gaps between students at the tertiary level (Meir & Fletcher, 2020). However, the study findings articulated that sports festivals removed gender and racial barriers among students in high education (Hastie, Martinez, & Luquin, 2011).

The crux of the study asserted that physical education and sports festivals enhanced leadership and teamwork skills among diverse backgrounds of students in higher education (Wang & Chen, 2021). Similarly, the study findings outlined that sports tournaments and extracurricular activities promoted behavioral and ethical values in higher education (Luguetti et al., 2019). Likewise, the research revealed that extracurricular activities and festivals as a tool for conflict resolution and created a sense of tolerance among students at high education levels (Kausar, Manaf, & Shoaib, 2022; Kristiansen, 2017). Further, the crux of the study indicated that sports festivals enhanced responsibilities and discipline among different students at the tertiary level (Kohe, Jamie, & Hughson, 2023; Shoaib, Naseer, & Naseer, 2023). Moreover, the study asserted that sports festivals and playing on common grounds minimized the diversity among university students (Kohe & Collison, 2020). In the same way, the search findings argued that sports festivals promoted respect and equal rights without any discrimination in higher education (Durbin, 2020; Shoaib, Mehmood, & Butt, 2022). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that sports festivals promoted gender dynamics at a high education level (Stevenson & Clegg, 2012). However, the study findings articulated that sports festivals improved the participation of girls in physical activities and sports tournaments (Dagkas, Tansin, & Jawad, 2011).

The study argued that quizzes and debate competitions influenced the student's participation in political affairs at a high education level (Asamoah, 2017). Similarly, the study findings outlined that participating in quiz competitions enhanced learning and critical thinking among different students in high education (Cook & Babon, 2017). Likewise, the research revealed that quiz and debate competition as a source of political expression and shared their perspectives in higher education (Yeo & Li, 2014). Further, the crux of the study indicated that debate competition provided the facility for each student to openly share their point of view at a high education level (Min & Dongying, 2007). Moreover, the study asserted that quiz competition boosted memory and logical reasoning among diverse students at the tertiary level (Abichandani et al., 2024). In the same way, the search findings argued that quiz and debate competitions give a chance to represent students from different backgrounds, cultures, and ethnicities in higher education (S. Park, 2005). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that quiz and debate competitions enhance the confidence of the students in public speaking on different matters (McIntosh & Milam,

2016). However, the study findings articulated that participation in quiz and debate competitions raised the confidence level of students from different backgrounds, classes, and ethnicities to highlight their interests and needs at the university level (Nakao, JoAnn, & Volland, 2013).

The analysis of the study pointed out that quiz and debate competitions promoted inclusive learning and time management among university students (Calimeris & Kosack, 2020). Similarly, the study findings outlined that quiz and debate competitions engaged students in openly religious discussion, understanding, and respect of different religious points of view in higher education (Grosvenor & Pataki, 2017). Likewise, the research revealed that participation in quiz and debate competitions encouraged students to research different topics and religious activities at the university level (Johnston, & Loughlin, 2023). Further, the crux of the study indicated that quiz and debate competitions empowered students from the low-class and disadvantaged groups at the tertiary level (Bourner & Heath, 2014). Moreover, the study asserted that quiz and debate competitions promoted equal rights by following quiz rules and winning debates with strong points in higher education (Jung, 2014). In the same way, the search findings argued that quiz competition enhanced the value of weekly quizzes and social learning among university students (Haigh, 2007). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that participating in quiz and debate competitions helped different residential background students to exchange their ideas at a higher education level (Withers, Alexandra, & McCool, 2021). However, the study findings articulated that participation in quiz and debate competitions encouraged social mobility and empowerment of marginalized groups in higher education (Turner, 2008).

Theoretical Framework

This study has been conducted using social learning theory (Albert, 1977). The theory focuses on individual behaviors that are not learned from personal experiences. Learning is a cognitive process that takes place by observing other people's actions and their outcomes. In higher education, students observe each other and learn how to behave, how to treat others, and how to act in specific situations. Extracurricular activities are informal in nature but provide powerful settings for such learning. These activities bring students from different cultural, religious, and residential areas together. Through participation in volunteer activities, sports festivals, and seminar activities, students meet different people, work with them, and observe them. This learning changes students' perspectives and behaviors. Students learn what actions are rewarded and discouraged. Students observe inclusive behaviors and use respectful dialogue in debates and discussions for minorities. Bandura Bobo doll experiments strongly support this study that show behavior of children depends on their adults' actions. Students learn inclusive behaviors by watching their role models, such as parents, teachers, or peer groups. They adopt these behaviors in their actions and roles. In extracurricular activities, students work in groups that shape their attitudes toward equality, justice, and diversity. Students also learn tolerance, empathy, and mutual respect promoting an inclusive atmosphere in the university. These behaviors accept the differences and break down the traditional barriers. However, the social learning theory highlights the idea that meaningful interactions during extracurricular activities to learn and develop inclusive values that create a respectful and inclusive environment in higher education. These consumptions have been linked with this study. Students have learned a lot of co-curricular and extracurricular activities at the university, which results in creating an inclusive learning environment. It has also been observed that extracurricular activities promote diversity and inclusion among students. Hence, the assumption of the above-mentioned theory has been used and linked within the study.

The Data and Methods

This study has been conducted using a quantitative approach and students of the BS (4 Years) program of the sociology and economics department of the public sector university constitute the population of the study. A sampling frame has been collected and a sample of 213 students (calculated using sample size determination formula i.e., $n=1+N(e)^2$) has been selected using a proportionate random sampling technique. An equal proportion has been given to each department. A cross-sectional survey has been conducted and a structured questionnaire has been finalized after pretesting to collect the data. The value of Alpha has been found .700 and above. Statistical analysis has been made using Chi-Square and regression analysis tests. Further, the results have been presented in the results and discussion section.

Results and Discussion

This section provides the results of primary data analysis and presents them in the form of Chi-Square and regression analysis statistical tests.

Table 1*Chi-Square Statistics Tests (Dependent Variable = Diversity and Inclusion, n=213)*

Independent Variables	Pearson Chi-Square Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Quiz and Debate Competitions	1626.848 ^a	1334	.000
Volunteer Activities	1297.222 ^a	1102	.000
Seminar and Workshop Activities	1535.779 ^a	1218	.000
Extracurricular Activities	4318.467 ^a	3828	.000
Age and Gender	1446.110 ^a	1160	.000
Political Affiliation	1397.513 ^a	1160	.000
Religious Affiliation	1609.301 ^a	1160	.000
Intersectionality of Class	1305.059 ^a	1102	.000
Residential Background	1564.332 ^a	1044	.000
Cultural Differences	1357.364 ^a	1044	.000

Table 1 asserted the study of Chi-Square statistical tests using diversity and inclusion as dependent variables. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1624.848$, df 1334, $p = .000$) between quiz and debate competitions and the diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1297.222$, df 1102, $p = .000$) between volunteer activities and the diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1535.779$, df 1218, $p = .000$) between seminar and workshop activities and diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 4318.467$, df 3828, $p = .000$) between extracurricular activities and the diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1446.110$, df 1160, $p = .000$) between age and gender and diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1397.513$, df 1160, $p = .000$) between political affiliation and diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1609.301$, df 1160, $p = .000$) between religious affiliation and diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1305.059$, df 1102, $p = .000$) between the intersectionality of class and diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1564.332$, df 1044, $p = .000$) between residential background and the diversity and inclusion of students in higher education. The statistical analysis indicated that there was an association ($\chi^2= 1357.364$, df 1044, $p = .000$) between cultural differences and diversity and inclusion of students in higher education.

Table 2*OLS Multiple Regression Analysis Predicting Diversity and Inclusion of the Students (Standards Error and Parameter Estimates)*

Predictors	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Intersectionality of Class	1.458	.160	.349	9.094	.000
Residential Background	1.242	.165	.281	7.525	.000
Cultural Differences	1.561	.152	.383	10.276	.000
Extracurricular Activities	.153	.032	.171	4.864	.000
(Constant)	19.071	4.505		4.233	.000

R=.889, R Square=.790, Adjusted R Square=.786, F=196.136, Sig=.000, n=213

Table 2 distributed the OLS multiple regression analysis predicting diversity and inclusion of the students (standards error and parameter estimates). The results of regression analysis pointed out that intersectionality of class, residential background, cultural differences, and extracurricular activities had favorable effects on diversity and inclusion and students in higher education. Similarly, the analysis of the research had been confirmed with p-values less than 0.05.

Figure 1
Showing Histogram

The analysis of the study pointed out that participation in outdoor non-academic activities supported social interaction irrespectively ethnicity, class, and religious background among students (Remmen, Marie, & Höper, 2021). Similarly, the study findings outlined that outdoor non-academic activities expand social networks and promote diversity among students in high education (Peacock, April, Kevin, & McInnis, 2021). Moreover, the study asserted that physical activities, outdoor learning, and outdoor non-academic activities enhanced health and positive learning about diversity (Romar, Ida, Janne, Jouni, & Tammelin, 2019). In the same way, the search findings argued that outdoor non-academics provided neutral space and supported gender equality among students at high education levels (Nakutin & Gutierrez, 2019). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that outdoor non-academic activities boosted self-confidence and self-discovery among students from diverse backgrounds in high education (Caldas & Reilly, 2019). However, the study findings articulated that creativity activities, physical activities, and outdoor non-academic activities helped students to respect diverse norms and values at the tertiary level (Hyndman & Mahony, 2018). Likewise, the research revealed that outdoor non-academic activities, outdoor education, and physical activities boosted the learning of low-income students and urban students (Breivik, 2021). Further, the analysis of the study pointed out that outdoor non-academic activities strengthen social connection and reduce social isolation (Vasold, & Pivarnik, 2020).

The primary data analysis asserted that diversity and inclusion through high education are influenced by anti-diversity, equity, and inclusion climates (Montelongo, Silvestre, & Richardson, 2025). Similarly, the study findings outlined that diversity and inclusion are promoted by extracurricular activities in higher education (Rivera, Sanders, & DeJong, 2025). Likewise, the research revealed that diversity and inclusion are supported by academic institutions concerning extracurricular activities (Muzamil, Shiraz, Iqbal, Shah, & Khan, 2024). Further, the crux of the study indicated that diversity, equity, and inclusion are measured by co-curricular activities in higher education (Cumming, Miller, & Leshchinskaya, 2023). Moreover, the study asserted that diversity had been found among students in different departments about extracurricular activities (Kong & Chen, 2022). In the same way, the search findings argued that diversity and inclusion are promoted by business, higher education, and extracurricular activities (Prasetio, Waspada, & Mulyadi, 2024). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that diversity and inclusion positively impacted extracurricular activities and social services organizations among students in higher education (Cano, 2020). However, the study findings articulated that diversity and inclusion supported representations of students and the reality of extracurricular activities at high education levels (Richards, Pilcher, Galbrun, Forster, & Richards, 2023).

The argument based on the study findings clinched that diversity was found in university policies for inclusive participation in the extracurricular activities of students (Raja, Lambert, Patlamazoglou, & Pringle, 2024). Similarly, the study findings outlined that universities that promoted diversity and inclusion encouraged several students to take part in extracurricular activities (Amin, Yasin, & Rutkowska-Ziarko, 2023). Likewise, the research revealed that diversity and inclusion ensured campus unity and minimized barriers to participating in extracurricular activities (Tamtik & Balasubramaniam, 2024). Further, the crux of the study indicated that diversity and inclusion created a safe environment for all students to participate in extracurricular activities (Iniesto & Bossu, 2023). Moreover, the study asserted that diversity and inclusion positively promoted the academic achievement and professional skills of students through involvement in extracurricular activities (Soroski, Hove, Steblecki, & Yu, 2024). In the same way, the search findings argued that a diverse and inclusive environment helped students to work together and take part in outdoor non-academic activities (DeDiego, Basma, Chan, & Farrell, 2024). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that diversity and inclusion provided a platform for students to gain experience by participating in extracurricular activities at the tertiary level (Tavares, 2024). However, the study findings articulated that diversity and inclusion created a social network between higher education students by involving extracurricular activities (Posselt, 2023).

The study pointed out that diversity promoted gender equality and welcomed all students to take part in extracurricular activities in higher education (Haitembu, 2023). Similarly, the study findings outlined that diversity and inclusion support language differences between students and respect in extracurricular activities at high education level (Piller & Takahashi, 2011). Likewise, the research revealed that diversity and inclusion managed and regulated student communities and extracurricular activities in higher education (Scott, 2020). Further, the crux of the study indicated that diversity and inclusion maintained racially and ethnically unrepresented students through extracurricular activities at high education levels (Trolian, 2015). Moreover, the study asserted that diversity and inclusion multiply redefined by students how they access and think after joining extracurricular activities at the tertiary level (Weissmann, Ibarra, Howland-Davis, & Lammey, 2019). In the same way, the search findings argued that diversity and inclusion advocated equality, crisis, and compliance with extracurricular activities among higher education students (Smith & Gasman, 2025). As mentioned in the study analysis reported that diversity and inclusion changed the socio-political and legal landscape among students associated with extracurricular activities at higher education levels (McGowan, Rodney, Lia, & Leopold, 2025). However, the study findings articulated that diversity and inclusion maintained anti-diversity, equality, and inclusive environments among students through extracurricular activities (Cho & Mor Barak, 2008).

Conclusion

The study concludes that the intersectionality of cultural identity, socio-economic class, residential background, and participation in extracurricular activities positively affects the diversity and inclusion of students at higher educational institutions. Among these factors, extracurricular activities emerged as particularly significant in fostering inclusive environments and promoting student engagement across diverse backgrounds in different disciplines. Further, these activities including sports festivals, academic seminars, quiz competitions, student gatherings, volunteer work, and outdoor other non-academic events played a very important role in creating spaces for mutual understanding, collaboration, and interaction. The study also concludes that indicators of diversity and inclusion extend beyond traditional demographic markers such as age and gender, encompassing political, and religious affiliations as well as the broader intersectional dimensions of students' lived experiences. This paper emphasizes that expressive involvement in extracurricular activities adds to building inclusive academic communities where dissimilar identities are acknowledged, respected, and integrated into the social fabric of university life.

References

- Abernathy, C., & Forestal, J. (2020). Civics Across Campus: Designing Effective Extracurricular Programming. *Journal of Political Science Education*, 16(1), 3-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15512169.2018.1512870>
- Abichandani, P., Deepan, L., Branislav, D., Ashish, B., Jaskirat, S., Smit, K., . . . Kam, M. (2024). Competition-based active learning instruction for drone education. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(5), 1795-1813. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2128821>
- Ahmad, S. (2020). Political behavior in virtual environment: Role of social media intensity, internet connectivity, and political affiliation in online political persuasion among university students. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 30(4), 457-473. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2019.1698485>
- Albert, B. (1977). *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1): Prentice hall Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- Ali, R., Zaman, M. A., & Shoaib, M. (2024). Trends of Research Visualization of Gender Inequality, Equality, and Equity: A Bibliometric Analysis from 1981 to 2020. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(8), 237-252.
- Aliu, J., & Aigbavboa, C. (2023). Reviewing the roles of extracurricular activities in developing employability skills: a bibliometric review. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 23(10), 1623-1632. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15623599.2021.1995807>
- Amin, S., Yasin, I., & Rutkowska-Ziarko, A. (2023). Diversity-inclusion nexus: assessing the role of ethnic and religious diversity in financial inclusion; a global perspective. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 36(1), 1205-1225. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2022.2083648>
- Arshad, H. K., Anwar, B., & Shoaib, M. (2024a). Nexus of Classroom Environment and English Language Learning Skills in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), 58-67.
- Arshad, H. K., Anwar, B., & Shoaib, M. (2024b). Teaching Spaces in Pakistan: A Case of English Language Learning Skills at Tertiary Level. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 5(3), 71-80.
- Asamoah, M. K. (2017). Access to undergraduate education is an unresolved burden in Ghana: A qualitative approach. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 36(5), 595-612. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2017.1356880>
- Berger, C., Cristian, B., & Espelage, D. L. (2021). Extracurricular activities and peer relational victimization: Role of gender and school social norms. *Journal of School Violence*, 20(4), 611-626. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2022.2026226>
- Betz, C. L., Gay, R., L., B. C., & Redcay, G. (2005). An Exploratory Study of Future Plans and Extracurricular Activities of Transition-Age Youth and Young Adults. *Issues in Comprehensive Pediatric Nursing*, 28(1), 33-61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01460860590916753>
- Boone, S., R., S. K., Natasha, B., & Smith, P. N. (2023). College extracurricular involvement as a suicide prevention and wellness promotion strategy: Exploring the roles of social support and meaning. *Journal of American College Health*, 71(3), 677-685. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2021.1904952>
- Bourner, T., & Heath, L. (2014). The pedagogic potential of the pub quiz. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 51(1), 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2013.778065>
- Breivik, G. (2021). 'Richness in Ends, Simplesness in Means!' on Arne Naess's Version of Deep Ecological Friluftsliv and Its Implications for Outdoor Activities. *Sport, Ethics and Philosophy*, 15(3), 417-434. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17511321.2020.1789719>
- Bundick, M. J. (2011). Extracurricular activities, positive youth development, and the role of meaningfulness of engagement. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 6(1), 57-74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439760.2010.536775>
- Caldas, S. J., & Reilly, M. S. (2019). The Mediating Influence of Physical Activity Levels on 3rd-Grade Academic Achievement. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 33(2), 271-289. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02568543.2019.1577775>
- Calimeris, L., & Kosack, E. (2020). Immediate feedback assessment technique (IF-AT) quizzes and student performance in microeconomic principles courses. *The Journal of Economic Education*, 51(3-4), 211-226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220485.2020.1804501>
- Cano, M. (2020). Diversity and Inclusion in Social Service Organizations: Implications for Community Partnerships and Social Work Education. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 56(1), 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10437797.2019.1656577>

- Cao, X. (2024). Case Study of China's Compulsory Education System: AI Apps and Extracurricular Dance Learning. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 40(13), 3419-3426. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2023.2188539>
- Chapman, G., Washad, E., & Obembe, D. (2023). Higher education student motivations for extracurricular activities: evidence from UK universities. *Journal of Education and Work*, 36(2), 138-152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2023.2167955>
- Cho, S., & Mor Barak, M. E. (2008). Understanding of Diversity and Inclusion in a Perceived Homogeneous Culture: A Study of Organizational Commitment and Job Performance Among Korean Employees. *Administration in Social Work*, 32(4), 100-126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03643100802293865>
- Cook, B. R., & Babon, A. (2017). Active learning through online quizzes: better learning and less (busy) work. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 41(1), 24-38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03098265.2016.1185772>
- Cumming, T., Miller, M. D., & Leshchinskaya, I. (2023). DEI Institutionalization: Measuring Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Postsecondary Education. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 55(1), 31-38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00091383.2023.2151802>
- Dagkas, S., Tansin, B., & Jawad, H. (2011). Multiple voices: improving participation of Muslim girls in physical education and school sport. *Sport, Education and Society*, 16(2), 223-239. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2011.540427>
- Darling, N., L., C. L., & Smith, R. (2005). Participation in School-Based Extracurricular Activities and Adolescent Adjustment. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 37(1), 51-76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222216.2005.11950040>
- DeDiego, A. C., Basma, D., Chan, C. D., & Farrell, I. C. (2024). Experiences of diversity, equity, and inclusion for doctoral students and new faculty in leadership development programs. *Journal of Counselor Leadership and Advocacy*, 11(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2326716X.2023.2239241>
- Durbin, D. T. (2020). From Plato to St. Paul: ancient sport as performative public discourse. *Journal of the Philosophy of Sport*, 47(3), 403-418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00948705.2020.1811108>
- Grosvenor, I., & Pataki, G. (2017). Learning through culture: seeking "critical case studies of possibilities" in the history of education. *Paedagogica Historica*, 53(3), 246-267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00309230.2016.1264981>
- Guest, A. M., Peter, S., & Maige, G. (2021). Integrating global and local best practices for youth development afterschool: Constructing the Kilimanjaro extracurriculars self-assessment. *Cogent Education*, 8(1), 1982600. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2021.1982600>
- Haigh, M. (2007). Sustaining learning through assessment: an evaluation of the value of a weekly class quiz. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 32(4), 457-474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930600898593>
- Haitembu, R. K. (2023). Gender and sexual diversity: Inclusion in the Namibian education context. *Cogent Education*, 10(2), 2253702. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2253702>
- Harris, S., & Houlihan, B. (2016). Competition or coalition? Evaluating the attitudes of National Governing Bodies of Sport and County Sport Partnerships towards School Sport Partnerships. *International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics*, 8(1), 151-171. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19406940.2015.1024708>
- Hastie, P. A., D., C.-S. M., D., K. G., & Wallhead, T. L. (2023). "Beyond My Wildest Dreams": The Reach and Impact of Sport Education. *Quest*, 75(1), 63-73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2022.2125408>
- Hastie, P. A., Martinez, d. O. D., & Luquin, A. C. (2011). A review of research on Sport Education: 2004 to the present. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 16(2), 103-132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2010.535202>
- Hlavac, M. (2016). Performance of political parties in the 2016 parliamentary election in Slovakia: regional comparisons and district-level determinants. *Regional & Federal Studies*, 26(3), 433-443. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597566.2016.1178114>
- Hordósy, R., & Clark, T. (2018). Beyond the compulsory: a critical exploration of the experiences of extracurricular activity and employability in a northern red brick university. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 23(3), 414-435. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2018.1490094>
- Hyndman, B., & Mahony, L. (2018). Developing creativity through outdoor physical activities: a qualitative exploration of contrasting school equipment provisions. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 18(3), 242-256. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2018.1436078>
- Iniesto, F., & Bossu, C. (2023). Equity, diversity, and inclusion in open education: A systematic literature review. *Distance Education*, 44(4), 694-711. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587919.2023.2267472>

- Johnston, P. R., J., W. D., L., B. C., L., W. M., & Loughlin, W. A. (2023). Online quiz for STEM assumed knowledge self-assessment by first year science students: a pilot study. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 54(5), 782-800. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2021.1968050>
- Jung, J. H. (2014). Playing with New Rules: Radio Quiz Shows and the Reorientation of the Japanese Under the US Occupation, 1945–1952. *Historical Journal of Film, Radio and Television*, 34(4), 568-585. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01439685.2013.858939>
- Katsogridakis, G., & Leather, M. (2025). Teacher-student relationships in higher education: reflections from an adventure sport context. *Sport, Education and Society*, 30(2), 237-248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2023.2298794>
- Kausar, N., Manaf, A., & Shoaib, M. (2022). Suicidal Ideation among Adolescents: A Case of Bullying Victimization and Emotional Intelligence. *OMEGA - Journal of Death and Dying*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00302228221120123>
- Keser, F., Hanife, A., & Yildirim, A. (2011). The role of extracurricular activities in active citizenship education. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 43(6), 809-837. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220272.2011.591433>
- Kim, J., & Bastedo, M. N. (2017). Athletics, clubs, or music? The influence of college extracurricular activities on job prestige and satisfaction. *Journal of Education and Work*, 30(3), 249-269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2016.1165341>
- King, A. E., E., M. F. A., & Brigham, S. M. (2021). Exploring the Relationship Between Student Success and Participation in Extracurricular Activities. *SCHOLE: A Journal of Leisure Studies and Recreation Education*, 36(1-2), 42-58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1937156X.2020.1760751>
- Kohe, G. Z., & Collison, H. (2020). Playing on common ground: spaces of sport, education and corporate connectivity, contestation and creativity. *Sport in Society*, 23(1), 56-71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17430437.2018.1555219>
- Kohe, G. Z., Jamie, S., & Hughson, J. (2023). #hoops #basketballhistory @Hoops_Heritage: examining possibilities for basketball heritage within the context of higher education, critical museology and digital redirections. *Sport in History*, 43(3), 354-377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17460263.2021.1952481>
- Kong, D., & Chen, J. (2022). Diversity and inclusion in global higher education: Lessons from across Asia. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 59(2), 237-238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2022.2041960>
- Kristiansen, E. (2017). Walking the line: how young athletes balance academic studies and sport in international competition. *Sport in Society*, 20(1), 47-65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17430437.2015.1124563>
- Kwiatkowski, G., Ove, O., Anne-Mette, H., & Maristuen, H. (2020). The assemblers of rural festivals: organizers, visitors and locals. *European Planning Studies*, 28(2), 255-272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2019.1651829>
- Luguetti, C., Anne, G. V., & André, M. H. (2019). ‘That is like a 24 hours-day tournament!’: using social media to further an authentic sport experience within sport education. *Sport, Education and Society*, 24(1), 78-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2017.1292235>
- Mackintosh, C. (2014). Dismantling the school sport partnership infrastructure: findings from a survey of physical education and school sport practitioners. *Education 3-13*, 42(4), 432-449. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2012.714793>
- McGowan, B. L., Rodney, H., Lia, E., & Leopold, M. (2025). Navigating the Backlash and Reimagining Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in a Changing Sociopolitical and Legal Landscape. *Journal of College and Character*, 26(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2194587X.2024.2441300>
- McIntosh, J., & Milam, M. (2016). Competitive debate as competency-based learning: civic engagement and next-generation assessment in the era of the common core learning standards. *Communication Education*, 65(4), 420-433. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634523.2016.1203007>
- Meir, D., & Fletcher, T. (2020). The physical education and sport premium: Social justice, autonomy and school sport policy in England. *International Journal of Sport Policy and Politics*, 12(2), 237-253. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19406940.2019.1673790>
- Metsäpelto, R.-L., & Pulkkinen, L. (2012). Socioemotional Behavior and School Achievement in Relation to Extracurricular Activity Participation in Middle Childhood. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 56(2), 167-182. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2011.581681>

- Min, W., & Dongying, W. (2007). The China National Geography Competition for Middle School Students. *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 16(3), 280-282. <https://doi.org/10.2167/irgee211B.0>
- Montelongo, R., Silvestre, G. J., & Richardson, T. A. P. (2025). Aqui Estamos, No Nos Vamos: Storytelling to Navigate Anti-Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Climates. *Journal of College and Character*, 26(1), 74-83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2194587X.2024.2441298>
- Montepare, J. M., S., F. K., Anne, D., & Dixon, J. (2019). Becoming an Age-Friendly University (AFU): Integrating a retirement community on campus. *Gerontology & Geriatrics Education*, 40(2), 179-193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701960.2019.1586682>
- Muzamil, M., Shiraz, M., Iqbal, F., Shah, G. H., & Khan, M. A. (2024). College students' perceptions about academic institutions' support for diversity and inclusion in Pakistan. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2426976. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2426976>
- Nakao, K. C., JoAnn, D.-R., P., L. F., & Volland, P. J. (2013). Examination of the Psychometric Properties of the Knowledge of Aging for Social Work Quiz. *Educational Gerontology*, 39(10), 761-771. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601277.2012.734169>
- Nakutin, S. N., & Gutierrez, G. (2019). Effect of Physical Activity on Academic Engagement and Executive Functioning in Children With ASD. *School Psychology Review*, 48(2), 177-184. <https://doi.org/10.17105/SPR-2017-0124.V48-2>
- Naseer, N., Shoaib, M., & Naseer, A. (2022). Prevention is Better than Cure: An Evaluation of Preventive Measures Against COVID-19 Among Students at Tertiary Level. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(3), 1179-1192.
- O'Donnell, A. W., Gerry, R., A., G. A., J., W. J. J., & Mooney, A. (2024). Extracurricular activity participation, school belonging, and depressed mood: a test of the compensation hypothesis during adolescence. *Applied Developmental Science*, 28(4), 596-611. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2023.2260745>
- Park, J. J., Jia, Z., & Kim, B. H. (2023). Unveiling the Inequalities of Extracurricular Activities in Admissions. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 55(5), 45-54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00091383.2023.2235253>
- Park, S. (2005). Competition's Effects on Programming Diversity of Different Program Types. *International Journal on Media Management*, 7(1-2), 39-54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14241277.2005.9669415>
- Peacock, J., April, B., Kevin, F., & McInnis, K. (2021). Use of Outdoor Education to Increase Physical Activity and Science Learning among Low-Income Children from Urban Schools. *American Journal of Health Education*, 52(2), 92-100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19325037.2021.1877222>
- Pill, S., Dawn, P., John, W., Vaughan, C., & Hyndman, B. (2023). A Figurational Perspective on the Influence of the Sport Education Model in Australia. *Quest*, 75(1), 50-62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2022.2124183>
- Piller, I., & Takahashi, K. (2011). Linguistic diversity and social inclusion. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 14(4), 371-381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2011.573062>
- Posselt, J. R. (2023). From Innovations to Isomorphism in Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Efforts: Opportunities and Cautions for Higher Education. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 55(4), 33-41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00091383.2023.2213575>
- Prasetyo, B., Waspada, I., & Mulyadi, H. (2024). Diversity and Inclusion in Japan: Issues in Business and Higher Education. *Asian Affairs*, 55(1), 154-155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03068374.2024.2320292>
- Raja, A., Lambert, K., Patlamazoglou, L., & Pringle, R. (2024). Diversity and inclusion strategies for LGBTQ+ students from diverse ethnic backgrounds in higher education: a scoping review. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 28(14), 3585-3605. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2023.2217814>
- Remmen, K. B., Marie, J. K., & Höper, J. (2021). Preservice Teachers' Reflections on Outdoor Science Activities Following an Outdoor Chemistry Unit. *Journal of Science Teacher Education*, 32(4), 425-443. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1046560X.2020.1847967>
- Ribeiro, N., Carla, M., Tiago, N., & Menezes, I. (2024). The impact of extracurricular activities on university students' academic success employability. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 14(3), 389-409. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2023.2202874>
- Richards, K., Pilcher, N., Galbrun, L., Forster, A., & Richards, J. (2023). Diversity and inclusion in UK Higher Education: staff perspectives on institutional representations and their reality. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 28(4), 647-669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2023.2253654>

- Rivera, N., Sanders, K., & DeJong, C. (2025). The Case for Integrating Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion into Criminology and Criminal Justice Doctoral Programs. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 36(1), 165-186. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511253.2024.2398757>
- Romar, J.-E., Ida, E., Janne, K., Jouni, K., & Tammelin, T. (2019). Physical activity and sedentary behaviour during outdoor learning and traditional indoor school days among Finnish primary school students. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 19(1), 28-42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2018.1488594>
- Schönwälder, K. (2020). Diversity in local political practice. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 43(11), 1929-1941. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2020.1760329>
- Scott, C. (2020). Managing and Regulating Commitments to Equality, Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education. *Irish Educational Studies*, 39(2), 175-191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2020.1754879>
- Shoaib, M. (2021). *Sociological Analysis of Teachers Perspectives on Students Academic Performance in Higher Education in the Punjab*. (PhD Thesis). International Islamic University Islamabad, Central Library.
- Shoaib, M. (2023). Leisure and Psychological Well-being of the Elderly: Nexus of Mass Media and Modern Technology. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 2(2), 1042-1053.
- Shoaib, M. (2024a, January 09). Gender Disparity in Education. *The Nation*.
- Shoaib, M. (2024b). Gender Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(1), 207-222.
- Shoaib, M. (2024c, April 30). Gendered Space in Higher Education. *Daily Parliament Times*, p. 3.
- Shoaib, M. (2024d). Gendering Bourdieu's Cultural Capital in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(2), 265-278.
- Shoaib, M. (2024e). Tailoring Theoretical Lens and Nudging Bourdieu's Cultural Capital on Gender and Academic Performance. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 4(4), 87-101.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, N., Anwar, B., Rasool, S., Mustafa, R.-e., & Zici, S. (2021). Research Visualization on Teaching, Language, Learning of English and Higher Education Institutions from 2011 to 2020: A Bibliometric Evidences *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 5677, 1-27.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, R., & Akbar, A. (2021). Library Services and Facilities in Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan: Satisfaction of Patrons. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-19.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, S. R., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Self-Fulfilling Prophecy of Learning Skills Among Students in Higher Education. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(7), 164-177.
- Shoaib, M., Iqbal, S., & Tahira, G. (2021). Digitalization of Academic Libraries in Higher Education Institutions during COVID-19 Pandemic. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-15.
- Shoaib, M., Mehmood, S., & Butt, S. M. (2022). Intention to Leave a Job among Public Sector University Teachers: A Case of Work Environment. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(2), 370-383.
- Shoaib, M., Naseer, A., & Naseer, N. (2023). Family Pressure, Social Media Influence, and COVID-19 Vaccination Hesitancy among Students at Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 2(3), 295-307.
- Shoaib, M., Shehzadi, K., & Abbas, Z. (2024a). Inclusivity and Teachers' Aptitude in Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(6), 219-237.
- Shoaib, M., Shehzadi, K., & Abbas, Z. (2024b). Inclusivity, Teacher Competency, and Learning Environment at Higher Education: Empirical Evidences. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(5), 244-261.
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2019). Female and Male Students' Educational Performance in Tertiary Education in the Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Issues*, X(1), 83-100.
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2021). Teachers' perspectives on factors of female students' outperformance and male students' underperformance in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(3), 684-699. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-05-2020-0261>
- Shoaib, M., Usmani, F., & Abdullah, F. (2023). Plotting The Literature On Social Work Education From 1971-2020: A Scientometric Analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 5(2), 1347-1360.
- Shoaib, M., & Zaman, M. A. (2025). Evaluating Academic Performance in Higher Education during COVID-19 A Study of Virtual Learning Environments. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 4(4), 64-78.
- Shoaib, M., Zaman, M. A., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Trends of Research Visualization of Gender Based Violence (GBV) from 1971-2020: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(7), 203-216.

- Silverstein, N. M., Meghan, H., Marshall, B. L., J., F. W. A., & Whitbourne, S. K. (2019). Developing an Age-Friendly University (AFU) audit: A pilot study. *Gerontology & Geriatrics Education*, 40(2), 203-220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701960.2019.1572006>
- Simpkins, S. D., E., V. A., Y., D. M., & Price, C. D. (2012). Do School Friends Participate in Similar Extracurricular Activities?: Examining the Moderating Role of Race/Ethnicity and Age. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 44(3), 332-352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222216.2012.11950268>
- Simpkins, S. D., Megan, O. D., Y., D. M., & Becnel, J. N. (2011). Latino Adolescents' Participation in Extracurricular Activities: How Important Are Family Resources and Cultural Orientation? *Applied Developmental Science*, 15(1), 37-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2011.538618>
- Singer, J. N., & Cunningham, G. B. (2012). A case study of the diversity culture of an American university athletic department: perceptions of senior level administrators. *Sport, Education and Society*, 17(5), 647-669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2011.552572>
- Smith, S. L., & Gasman, M. (2025). Navigating Crisis and Compliance: Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Ban at the University of Alabama. *Journal of College and Character*, 26(1), 49-60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2194587X.2024.2439246>
- Soroski, T., Hove, K., Steblecki, L., & Yu, J. C. (2024). Evaluating the domains of generalism and equity, diversity and inclusion in preclinical simulated cases for targeted curricular improvements. *Medical Education Online*, 29(1), 2331852. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10872981.2024.2331852>
- Stamelos, G. K., Aggelos. (2011). The public debate on a quality assurance system for Greek universities. *Quality in Higher Education*, 17(3), 353-368. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2011.628807>
- Stevenson, J., & Clegg, S. (2012). Who cares? Gender dynamics in the valuing of extra-curricular activities in higher education. *Gender and Education*, 24(1), 41-55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2011.565039>
- Storr, R., & Spaaij, R. (2017). 'I guess it's kind of elitist': the formation and mobilisation of cultural, social and physical capital in youth sport volunteering. *Journal of Youth Studies*, 20(4), 487-502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13676261.2016.1241867>
- Tamtik, M., & Balasubramaniam, P. (2024). Equity, diversity, and inclusion in Canadian colleges: examining definitions and unveiling perceptions. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 48(7), 714-726. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2024.2386460>
- Tavares, V. (2024). Feeling excluded: international students experience equity, diversity and inclusion. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 28(8), 1551-1568. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2021.2008536>
- Tlalajoe-Mokhatla, N. (2024). Towards a conceptual framework in higher education anchored on social learning and social integration: transition, retention and graduation. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2409474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2409474>
- Trolian, T. L. (2015). Media Review: Diversity and Inclusion on Campus: Supporting Racially and Ethnically Underrepresented Students. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, 52(4), 455-457. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19496591.2015.1083439>
- Turner, I. J. (2008). Who Wants to be a Biologist? An Excellent Quiz Tool for Students. *Bioscience Education*, 11(1), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.3108/beej.11.c1>
- Vandell, D. L., Bradford, B. B., Dan, B., & Reisner, E. (2022). Afterschool programs, extracurricular activities, and unsupervised time: Are patterns of participation linked to children's academic and social well-being? *Applied Developmental Science*, 26(3), 426-442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2020.1843460>
- Vasold, K. L., & Pivarnik, J. M. (2020). Recreational Sports Participation and Academic Success: Numbers of Activities and Time Investment. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*, 57(5), 561-570. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19496591.2019.1689367>
- Villa-Lever, L. (2020). University spaces, gender and position of social origin: intersection of inequalities. *Gender and Education*, 32(4), 518-536. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2018.1501004>
- Wang, B., & Chen, S. (2021). Sport Education for Social Competence in K-12 Physical Education. *Quest*, 73(4), 391-409. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2021.1986410>
- Weissmann, G. S., Ibarra, R. A., Howland-Davis, M., & Lammey, M. V. (2019). The multicontext path to redefining how we access and think about diversity, equity, and inclusion in STEM. *Journal of Geoscience Education*, 67(4), 320-329. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10899995.2019.1620527>

- Withers, M., Alexandra, N., & McCool, J. (2021). University students' perspectives on tobacco control in the Asia-Pacific: a content analysis of a case competition. *International Journal of Health Promotion and Education*, 59(5), 286-296. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14635240.2020.1760118>
- Wong, M.-Y. (2023). University students' perceptions of learning of moral education: a response to lifelong moral education in higher education. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 28(3), 654-671. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2020.1852201>
- Xu, L., & Hu, Y. (2024). Managing the harmful effects of perceived overqualification amongst students in China: the roles of student leader and extracurricular activities. *Studies in Higher Education*, 49(2), 308-324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2023.2231952>
- Yemini, M., & Addi-Racah, A. (2013). School principals' agency as reflected by extracurricular activities in the Israeli education system. *International Studies in Sociology of Education*, 23(4), 358-382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09620214.2013.832524>
- Yeo, R. K., & Li, J. (2014). Beyond SERVQUAL: The competitive forces of higher education in Singapore. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 25(1-2), 95-123. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2011.637802>
- Zhang, D., & Tang, X. (2017). The influence of extracurricular activities on middle school students' science learning in China. *International Journal of Science Education*, 39(10), 1381-1402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2017.1332797>
- Zhang, W., & Veacock, C. (2023). Undergraduate Perceptions of Extracurricular and Co-Curricular Activities and Impact on Social Skills Development. *Chinese Education & Society*, 56(5-6), 392-412. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10611932.2024.2303929>